
Decaying Neutrino States in Beam Experiments

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Outline

- ◆ Introduction to neutrino oscillation
- ◆ Probabilities in presence of decay
- ◆ Octant sensitivity
- ◆ Degeneracies in θ_{23} - δ_{CP}

Neutrinos

β^- Decay

β^+ Decay

Terrestrial $\bar{\nu}_e$

Atmospheric ν

Astrophysical ν

- Three types of neutrinos ν_e, ν_μ, ν_τ
- Charge neutral leptons (fermions)
- Neutrinos are massless in SM.
- Participate in weak interaction.

Supernova ν

Solar $\bar{\nu}_e$

Big Bang ν

Neutrinos change identities

Reactor $\bar{\nu}_e$

Accelerator ν_μ

Standard Neutrino Oscillation

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} c_{12} & s_{12} & 0 \\ -s_{12} & c_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} c_{13} & 0 & s_{13}e^{-i\delta_{13}} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s_{13}e^{i\delta_{13}} & 0 & c_{13} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_{23} & s_{23} \\ 0 & -s_{23} & c_{23} \end{bmatrix}$$

Solar Reactor Atmospheric/LBL

$$H = \frac{1}{2E_\nu} U \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \Delta_{21} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \Delta_{31} \end{bmatrix} U^\dagger + \begin{bmatrix} A/2E_\nu & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

IC24 with SK atmospheric data		Normal Ordering (best fit)		Inverted Ordering ($\Delta\chi^2 = 6.1$)	
		bfp $\pm 1\sigma$	3σ range	bfp $\pm 1\sigma$	3σ range
	$\sin^2 \theta_{12}$	$0.308_{-0.011}^{+0.012}$	0.275 → 0.345	$0.308_{-0.011}^{+0.012}$	0.275 → 0.345
	$\theta_{12}/^\circ$	$33.68_{-0.70}^{+0.73}$	31.63 → 35.95	$33.68_{-0.70}^{+0.73}$	31.63 → 35.95
	$\sin^2 \theta_{23}$	$0.470_{-0.013}^{+0.017}$	0.435 → 0.585	$0.550_{-0.015}^{+0.012}$	0.440 → 0.584
	$\theta_{23}/^\circ$	$43.3_{-0.8}^{+1.0}$	41.3 → 49.9	$47.9_{-0.9}^{+0.7}$	41.5 → 49.8
	$\sin^2 \theta_{13}$	$0.02215_{-0.00058}^{+0.00056}$	0.02030 → 0.02388	$0.02231_{-0.00056}^{+0.00056}$	0.02060 → 0.02409
	$\theta_{13}/^\circ$	$8.56_{-0.11}^{+0.11}$	8.19 → 8.89	$8.59_{-0.11}^{+0.11}$	8.25 → 8.93
	$\delta_{CP}/^\circ$	212_{-41}^{+26}	124 → 364	274_{-25}^{+22}	201 → 335
	$\frac{\Delta m_{21}^2}{10^{-5} \text{ eV}^2}$	$7.49_{-0.19}^{+0.19}$	6.92 → 8.05	$7.49_{-0.19}^{+0.19}$	6.92 → 8.05
	$\frac{\Delta m_{3\ell}^2}{10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2}$	$+2.513_{-0.019}^{+0.021}$	+2.451 → +2.578	$-2.484_{-0.020}^{+0.020}$	-2.547 → -2.421

nuFit 6.0

Matter Effect

$$A = 2\sqrt{2}G_F N_e E_\nu = 7.6 \times 10^{-5} \frac{\rho}{\text{g/cc}} \frac{E_\nu}{\text{GeV}} \text{eV}^2$$

$$P_{\alpha\beta} = |\langle \nu_\alpha | \nu_\beta \rangle|^2 = \delta_{\alpha\beta} - 4 \sum_{i>j} \text{Re}(U_{\alpha i}^* U_{\beta i} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^*) \sin^2 \frac{1.27 \Delta_{ij} L}{E_\nu} + 2 \sum_{i>j} \text{Im}(U_{\alpha i}^* U_{\beta i} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^*) \sin \frac{2 \times 1.27 \Delta_{ij} L}{E_\nu}$$

- ⊛ $[\Delta_{ij} = m_i^2 - m_j^2]$: Δ_{21} (solar), Δ_{31} (atmospheric), θ_{12} (solar), θ_{13} (reactor), θ_{23} , Phase: δ_{CP}
- ⊛ Degeneracy in $\Delta_{31} - \delta_{CP}$ and $\theta_{23} - \delta_{CP}$

Invisible decay of Neutrinos

When ν_3 decays

$$H = \frac{1}{2E} U \left[\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \Delta m_{21}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \Delta m_{31}^2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -i\alpha_3 \end{pmatrix} \right] U^\dagger + \begin{pmatrix} A/2E & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\alpha_3 = m_3/\tau_3 \quad \kappa_3 = \alpha_3 L/E$$

- Decay parameter: α_3 (eV/s)
- Bi-magic baseline: 2540 km
- 2540 dependence on δ_{CP} is less
- At bi-magic baseline: $\sin[(A - 1)\Delta] = 0$
- Probe sensitivity to octant of θ_{23} , δ_{CP}

Oscillation Probabilities

$$P_{\mu e} = s_{13}^2 s_{23}^2 \left(1 + e^{-4\kappa_3} - 2e^{-2\kappa_3} + 4e^{-2\kappa_3} \sin^2[(\hat{A} - 1)\Delta] \right) \frac{\alpha_3^2 + \Delta_{31}^2}{\Delta_{31}^2 (\hat{A} - 1)^2 + \alpha_3^2} + \alpha s_{13} \sin 2\theta_{12} \sin 2\theta_{23} \frac{\sin \hat{A}\Delta}{\hat{A}} \times$$

$$\left[\left(\sin[(\hat{A} - 1)\Delta + \delta_{CP} - \Delta] e^{-2\kappa_3} + \sin[\hat{A}\Delta - \delta_{CP}] \right) \frac{\Delta_{31}^2 (\hat{A} - 1) - \alpha_3^2}{\Delta_{31}^2 (\hat{A} - 1)^2 + \alpha_3^2} + \left(\cos[\hat{A}\Delta - \delta_{CP}] - \cos[(\hat{A} - 1)\Delta + \delta_{CP} - \Delta] e^{-2\kappa_3} \right) \frac{A\alpha_3}{\Delta_{31}^2 (\hat{A} - 1)^2 + \alpha_3^2} \right]$$

$$P_{\mu\mu} = 1 - \frac{1}{2} \sin^2 2\theta_{23} [1 + 2 \sin^2 \Delta e^{-2\kappa_3} - e^{-2\kappa_3}] - s_{23}^2 (1 - e^{-4\kappa_3}) - \kappa_3 (4s_{23}^4 + \sin^2 2\theta_{23} \cos 2\Delta) - 4s_{13}^2 s_{23}^2 \frac{\sin^2[(\hat{A} - 1)\Delta]}{(\hat{A} - 1)^2}$$

$$- \frac{2}{\hat{A} - 1} s_{13}^2 \sin^2 2\theta_{23} \left(\sin \Delta \cos[\hat{A}\Delta] \frac{\sin[(\hat{A} - 1)\Delta]}{\hat{A}} - \frac{\hat{A}}{2} \Delta \sin[2\Delta] \right) + \alpha c_{12}^2 \sin^2 2\theta_{23} \Delta \sin[2\Delta] + \kappa_3^2 (8s_{23}^4 + \sin^2 2\theta_{23} \cos 2\Delta)$$

Degeneracies

- Separation b/w HO band and 41° curve around 4 GeV smaller in $P_{\mu e} \Rightarrow$ decreased sensitivity
- Separation between in $P_{\mu\mu}$ is higher for decay around 4 GeV \Rightarrow increased sensitivity

- Decrease in $P_{\mu e}, P_{\mu\mu}$ for lowering θ_{23} and higher value of decay \Rightarrow New degeneracy b/w $\theta_{23} - \alpha_3$

Experimental Specifications

2588 km (P2O)

- ◆ Water Cherenkov detector: 4 M ton
- ◆ Beam: 90 kW, POT: 4×10^{20} /yr
- ◆ Average density: 3.8 g/cc
- ◆ 2588 km is close to bimagic baseline
- ◆ Runtime: 3 yr(ν) + 3 yr($\bar{\nu}$)
- ◆ Peak energy: 2-3 GeV
- ◆ Relatively large background

1300 km (DUNE)

- ◆ Liquid Argon detector: 40 k ton
- ◆ Beam: 1.2 MW, POT: 10×10^{20} /yr
- ◆ Average density: 2.85 g/cc
- ◆ 1300 km baseline
- ◆ Runtime: 3.5 yr(ν) + 3.5 yr($\bar{\nu}$)
- ◆ Peak energy: 4-5 GeV
- ◆ Lesser background

Parameters	True values	Test values
θ_{12}	33.4°	33.4°
θ_{13}	8.42°	8.42°
θ_{23} (Hierarchy)	41°	$39^\circ : 51^\circ$
θ_{23} (Octant)	41° (49°)	$45^\circ : 51^\circ$ ($39^\circ : 45^\circ$)
δ_{CP}	$-180^\circ : 180^\circ$	$-180^\circ : 180^\circ$
δ_{CP} (CP sensitivity)	$-180^\circ : 180^\circ$	$-180^\circ, 0, 180^\circ$
Δm_{21}^2	7.53×10^{-5}	7.53×10^{-5}
Δm_{31}^2 (Hierarchy)	$\pm 2.45 \times 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2$	$\mp [2.35 : 2.6] \times 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2$
Δm_{31}^2 (Octant)	$\pm 2.45 \times 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2$	$\pm [2.35 : 2.6] \times 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2$
α_3^{-1}	$2.0 \times 10^{-11} \text{ s/eV}$	$[1.0 : 3.0] \times 10^{-11} \text{ s/eV}$

Table 1. The true and test values of oscillation parameters.

Events Spectrum

Octant of θ_{23} Sensitivity

Degeneracies in $\theta_{23} - \delta_{CP}$

Dot-dashed, dashed, and solid lines correspond to P2O, DUNE and P2O+DUNE combined analysis. Orange and blue colours stand for 5 σ , 3 σ contours.

DUNE+P2O removes all the wrong octant, wrong δ_{CP} solutions

Conclusions

- ◆ Sensitivity to octant increases for decay in P2O (2588 km) for θ_{23} in both HO and LO
- ◆ Octant sensitivity increases when θ_{23} in LO and decreases for θ_{23} in HO for decay
- ◆ Contribution of $\nu_{\mu}(\nu_e)$ channel in octant sensitivity is higher in 2588 km (1300 km).
- ◆ Joint analysis of DUNE, P2O removes wrong θ_{23} , wrong δ_{CP} solutions.
- ◆ We are also studying these degeneracies in presence of atmospheric neutrinos

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